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12 **Abstract**

13 We define consciousness as the category of all conscious experiences. This immediately raises
14 the question: What is the essence in which every conscious experience in the category of
15 conscious experiences partakes? We consider various abstract essences of conscious experiences
16 as theories of consciousness. They are: (i) conscious experience is an action of memory on
17 sensation, (ii) conscious experience is experiencing a particular as an exemplar of a general, (iii)
18 conscious experience is an interpretation of sensation, (iv) conscious experience is referring
19 sensation to an object as its cause, and (v) conscious experience is a model of stimulus.
20 Corresponding to each one of these theories we obtain a category of models of conscious
21 experiences: (i) category of actions, (ii) category of idempotents, (iii) category of two sequential
22 maps, (iv) category of brain-generalized figures, and (v) functor categories with intuition as base
23 and conceptual repertoire as exponent, respectively. For each theory of consciousness we also
24 calculate its truth value object and characterize the objective logic intrinsic to the corresponding
25 category of models of consciousness experiences.

26 **Introduction**

27 What is consciousness? Consciousness, according to Koch, “is everything you experience. It is
28 the tune stuck in your head, the sweetness of chocolate mousse, the throbbing pain of a
29 toothache, the fierce love for your child and the bitter knowledge that eventually all feelings will
30 end” (Koch, 2018, p. S9). This raises two foundational questions:

31 1. What is the nature of conscious experiences?

32 2. What is the nature of consciousness?

33 How are we to think of the totality of conscious experiences i.e., consciousness? How are we to
34 think of the constituents of consciousness i.e., conscious experiences? One obvious answer:
35 Conscious experiences are objects of the category of all conscious experiences and
36 consciousness is the category of conscious experiences. In other words, every conscious
37 experience has the essence of the category of conscious experiences, whatever the essence(s)
38 maybe. This characterization is in the spirit of asserting that a chair is an object of the category
39 of chairs.

40 Let us consider a visual experience: a face. A first-order approximation would represent the
41 experience as a point in a feature-space or as a set of features i.e., $\text{Face} = \{\text{eyes, nose, mouth}\}$
42 (Fodor, 1998). Sensory features are obviously structured, unlike the structureless elements of sets
43 (Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 1). Equally importantly, sensory features of a visual object
44 are related to one another in specific ways resulting in a cohesive object that is conscious
45 experience, which cannot be modelled as a set with its zero internal cohesion (Lawvere and

46 Schanuel, 2009, p. 146). Elementism, notwithstanding the Gestalt demonstrations (Albright et
47 al., 2000, p. S34), continues to be the default terminology as in analysing “perceptual experience
48 into a collection of simple sensory elements” (Albright, 2013a, p. 19). Along similar lines, mind
49 is defined as a set of brain functions (Bunge, 1981, p. 68; Kandel, 2013, p. 546). The claim that
50 ‘mind is a set’ is repeatedly asserted in the textbook *Principles of Neural Science* (Kandel et al.,
51 2013, p. 5, 334, 384), which takes on added significance in light of its pedagogical value in
52 training neuroscientists. Of course, this terminology does not reflect any failure to recognize that,
53 in terms of the above example of face perception, the constituent eyes, nose, and mouth, unlike
54 the structureless elements of a set, are figures of various shapes; these figures constituting a face
55 are related to one another in specific ways (cf. Croner and Albright, 1999). Nevertheless, it does
56 highlight the absence and the significance of having a conceptual repertoire that fits the reality of
57 conscious experiences. Here we put forward mathematical category as a construct suited for the
58 study of consciousness (Lawvere, 1994; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p. 21, 135-148). In line
59 with the commonplace understanding of the notion of category, a mathematical category consists
60 of objects all of which partake in the essence that is characteristic of the category; since every
61 object of the category partakes in the essence, the transformations of objects preserve the essence
62 (e.g. in the category of dogs, a transformation of an young dog into an old dog preserves the
63 “dogness”). We find that defining conscious experience as an object of the category of conscious
64 experiences, instead of as cohesion-less set of structure-less elements, provides the conceptual
65 repertoire—basic shapes, figures, and incidence relations—needed to reason about the essence of
66 conscious experiences and the essence-preserving transformations of conscious experiences.

68 **Theory of Conscious Experiences**

69 What is the essence of conscious experiences? Continuing with our example of face perception,
70 an experience of a face can be said to consist of figures of various shapes: two eye-shaped
71 figures, one nosed-shaped figure, and one mouth-shaped figure. Of these shapes, we can say that
72 eye, nose, and mouth are the basic shapes, and their incidence relations determine the mutual
73 relations between various basic-shaped figures constituting the face (Lawvere and Schanuel,
74 2009, pp. 82-83, 250-253, 369-371). When considering conscious experience in general, we may
75 treat sensory features (e.g. colour, shape), modalities (visual, tactile, etc.), and emotion, among
76 others, as basic shapes. For illustration, anger (in conscious experience) can be considered as an
77 emotion-shaped figure (in the experience) just as redness can be thought of as a colour-shaped
78 figure. The mutual relations between basic shapes, say, emotion and colour, determine the
79 mutual relations between figures of the corresponding shapes (anger and redness).

80 Basic shapes along with their incidence relations constitute the abstract essence or theory of the
81 category of conscious experiences (Lawvere, 2003, p. 215, 217; Lawvere, 2004a, pp. 10-12;
82 Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 154-155, 235-236; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 149-
83 151, 369-371). First, every experience has the essence [of the category of conscious experiences]
84 given by the basic shapes and their incidence relations. Next, every experience can be
85 represented as a structure formed of basic-shaped figures and their mutual relations induced by
86 the incidences of basic shapes (see Fig. 4 in Posina, Ghista, and Roy, 2017). Since every
87 experience has the essence of experiences, transformations of experiences are required to
88 preserve the essence of experiences, and as such are natural transformations (Lawvere and
89 Schanuel, 2009, p. 378). Geometrically speaking, natural transformations ‘do not tear’ the

90 structure transformed (ibid, p. 210). Philosophically, a natural transformation is: Becoming
91 consistent with Being (e.g. biological growth; Posina, 2016).

92 What are we to make of the totality of all conscious experiences along with their essence-
93 preserving transformations? Objects along with essence-preserving morphisms of objects form a
94 category. With experiences as objects [with a given structural essence] and essence-preserving
95 transformations of experiences as structure-preserving morphisms of objects, consciousness—the
96 totality of conscious experiences—can be construed as a category of conscious experiences. Note
97 that any experience can remain the same (identity transformation). If I went from sad to happy
98 and from happy to detached, then I went from sad to detached (composition of transformations of
99 experiences). Along these lines, other axioms and laws, which are required to be satisfied in
100 order for us to talk about a category of experiences, can be verified (Lawvere and Schanuel,
101 2009, p. 21, 149-160). Within this categorical framework, the structure of consciousness is an
102 external reflection of the structural essence of conscious experiences (Lawvere, 1972, p. 10).
103 More immediately, a category embodies a mode of cohesion (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p.
104 146), which is the most basic attribute of conscious experience. For example, parts of a body
105 (hands, legs, etc.) have a mode of cohesion, which is different from the mode of cohesion of
106 parts of a perceptual object (colour, shape). Note that ‘part’ is both itself and its relationship to
107 the whole (Lawvere, 1994, p. 53). Formally, a part of an object is not merely a subobject, but a
108 monomorphism specifying the inclusion of the subobject into the object (Lawvere and Schanuel,
109 2009, p. 335).

110 As illustrations of theory of a category and its basic shapes, we present simple theories
111 (abstract essences) of conscious experiences (in the spirit of Lawvere, 1999). More explicitly, the

112 mathematical method, according to F. William Lawvere, “consists of taking the main structure
113 [of an object] by itself as a first approximation to a theory of the object, i.e. mentally operating as
114 though all further structure of the object simply did not exist” (Lawvere, 1972, pp. 9-10). An
115 example of an abstract theory of conscious experiences is ‘particular as an exemplar of a general’
116 (cf. categorical perception; Albright, 2013b, pp. 628-630; Grossberg, 1976), whose models form
117 a category of idempotents (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 99-106), with exemplar as its basic
118 shape. The truth value object of the category of idempotents has three global truth values. With
119 ‘interpretation of sensation’ (Albright and Stoner, 1995; Croner and Albright, 1999; Schlack and
120 Albright, 2007) as a theory of conscious experiences, we obtain a category of two sequential
121 processes as the category of conscious experiences. Here, the basic shapes are physical stimuli,
122 neural sensation of stimuli, and conscious interpretation of sensation. With conscious experience
123 as an object of the category of two sequential functions, we find that the objective logic intrinsic
124 to consciousness has four truth values (Posina, Ghista, and Roy, 2017, pp. 172-174). We also
125 consider ‘action of memory on sensation’ (Albright, 2012, Fig. 5, 8; Hopfield, 1982; Lawvere
126 and Schanuel, 2009, p. 218), ‘referring sensation to an object as its cause’ (Albright, 2015, p. 22;
127 Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 125-126, 148-152), and ‘model of stimulus’ (Chalmers,
128 2006; Posina, Ghista, and Roy, 2017) as theories of conscious experiences.

129 Given a category of experiences, how do we abstract the theory (essence) of experiences?
130 Theorization begins with measurements of properties of the objects of the given category.
131 Oftentimes, we find that there is small subcategory of properties (and their determinations)
132 within the category of all properties that constitutes the abstract essence shared by all objects of
133 the given category. This abstract essence in which every object of a given category partakes is

134 the theory of the given category (Lawvere, 1994, pp. 44-47; Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp.
135 154-155; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 149-150; see also Fig. 5 in Posina, Ghista, and Roy,
136 2017). In geometric terminology, we consider a subcategory of basic shapes and their incidence
137 relations, and examine if figures with objects in the subcategory as shapes are adequate to
138 completely characterize every object of the category and tell apart transformations between
139 objects (Lawvere, 1994, p. 49; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 369-371). In the following we
140 focus on the calculation of truth value objects corresponding to various theories of conscious
141 experiences and the subsequent characterization of the objective logic intrinsic to various
142 categories of models of conscious experiences (ibid, pp. 335-357).

143

144 **Action of Memory on Sensation**

145 Conscious experience of a given physical stimulus can be thought of as an action of memory on
146 the sensation elicited by the stimulus (for a vivid illustration of the action of memory on
147 sensation, see Fig. 5 and 8 in Albright, 2012). A formalization of conscious experience as an
148 action of memory on sensation is provided by Hopfield (1982). Here sensation S is a $1 \times n$
149 feature vector, with each one of the elements of the vector S representing the activity of each one
150 of the n feature-selective neurons. Memory M , or the $n \times n$ synaptic weight matrix, is a result of
151 associative learning, and can be expressed as a product of the sensation S with its transpose S^T ,
152 i.e.

153

$$M = S^T \times S$$

154 Conscious experience $C(S)$ corresponding to sensation S is:

$$155 \quad C(S) = S \times M.$$

156 For a given memory, conscious experiences corresponding to various sensations have the
 157 structure of idempotents (as discussed in detail in appendix A1). Categorical perception, wherein
 158 particulars (stimuli) are perceived as exemplars of a general (category; Albright, 2013b, pp. 628-
 159 630), also has the structure of idempotents. The abstract essence or theory of the category of
 160 idempotents consists of one basic shape: exemplar, along with an idempotent endomap as the
 161 structural map. Unlike the classical Boolean logic of sets, we find that the truth value object of
 162 the category of idempotents consists of three truth values. Also, two dual forms of negation—
 163 *not*, *non*—can be defined (Lawvere, 1986, 1991). We find that double negation can be greater or
 164 less than identity depending on the exact nature of negation. Furthermore, the category of
 165 idempotents admits logical contradiction (Lawvere, 2003, p. 214-215; or boundary operation
 166 defined as the intersection of a part with its negation; Lawvere, 1994, p. 48; Lawvere and
 167 Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 201).

168

169 **Interpretation of Sensation**

170 Conscious experience involves two sequential processes of sensation (of stimulus) followed by
 171 interpretation of the sensation. A classic illustration of the two sequential processes involved in
 172 conscious experience is R. C. James's image (Miller, 1999). When looking at the image one
 173 initially sees black and white blobs of various sizes and shapes, which subsequently, in light of

174 the concept DALMATIAN, is perceptually interpreted as a dog. That conscious experience is
 175 mediated by the two processes of sensation followed by interpretation is well-established in
 176 various perceptual modalities (e.g. Albright and Stoner, 1995; Croner and Albright, 1999). Thus
 177 the abstract theory of consciousness consists of three basic shapes i.e. objects (Physical Stimuli,
 178 Neural Codes, and Conscious Experiences) and two incidence relations i.e. maps (*sensation* and
 179 *interpretation*) organized as shown below:

180 Physical Stimuli --sensation-- Neural Codes $\text{--interpretation--}$ Conscious Experiences

181 The truth value object of the category of models of conscious experiences of the above theory of
 182 consciousness consists of four global truth values (Fig. 6c in Posina, Ghista, and Roy, 2017
 183 depicts the internal diagram of the truth value object; see Appendix A2 in Posina and Roy, 2018
 184 for the calculation of the truth value object; see also Linton, 2005).

185

186 **Brain-generalized Figures**

187 Everyday experience of effectively interacting with objects of conscious experience indicates
 188 that conscious experience of objects is recovery of the objects based on the sensation elicited by
 189 the objects (i.e. constructing an object isomorphic to the cause of sensation; Albright, 2015, p.
 190 22; Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 125-126, 148-152). In reconstructing objects in conscious
 191 experience, we encounter the possibility of not only the commonplace isomorphism between
 192 objects and conscious experience of objects, but also illusory conscious experiences with no
 193 correspondent underlying objects. We now present a mathematical framework rich enough to

194 capture both veridical perception and illusions (Lawvere, 2004b). Given a stimulus A , we define
195 sensation p as a brain V -valued property of the stimulus A , i.e.

$$196 \quad p: A \rightarrow V$$

197 Next, we consider brain V -valued properties of sensations, i.e.

$$198 \quad q: V^A \rightarrow V$$

199 which may be considered as a special case of interpretation of sensation, i.e. a neural measure of
200 sensation. Perceived element is defined as a brain V -generalized point of A satisfying naturality
201 conditions (discussed in detail in appendix A2). Within this mathematical framework, we find
202 that defining brain V as neuronal states of ‘firing’ and ‘not firing’, i.e. as a two-element property
203 type, can give rise to illusions. However, defining brain V in terms of all possible changes in
204 neuronal firing rate, i.e. as a three-element set $V = \{\text{decreased firing rate, constant firing rate,}$
205 $\text{increased firing rate}\}$, ensures illusion-free perception, or isomorphism between elements of a
206 stimulus set and perceived elements. As we have been emphasizing, physical stimuli, neural
207 sensations, and conscious experiences are much more structured than structureless sets; as such
208 we are working on refining the mathematical framework to accommodate conscious experience
209 defined as brain-generalized figure of stimuli (for basic shapes and their incidences of the
210 categories corresponding to physical stimuli and neural sensation).

211

212

213 **Model of Physical Stimulus**

214 Of the various abstract essences (theories) of conscious experiences, the most basic
215 characterization of conscious experience is: conscious experience of a stimulus is a model of the
216 stimulus (Chalmers, 2006). This immediately suggests functorial semantics, which provides a
217 mathematical account of constructing models of particulars, as an abstract theory of conscious
218 experience (Lawvere, 1994, 2004a). Given a category of physical stimulus, a model or conscious
219 experience of the stimulus is calculated by abstracting the essence (mental concepts) of its brain-
220 valued properties i.e. sensation. Thus abstracted mental concepts are then interpreted into a
221 background category of intuition to obtain models of the physical stimuli or conscious
222 experiences. The objective logic of conscious experiences construed as functor categories, with
223 intuition as base and mental concepts as exponent, is not classical (Posina, Ghista, and Roy,
224 2017). Furthermore, subjectivity (understood as viewpoint; cf. Sen, 1993) is captured by the
225 framework of functorial semantics; more specifically, the mathematical construct of monad
226 determines how a category of particulars is [subjectively] generalized into the adjoint pair of
227 functors: mental concepts (theories) and conscious percepts (defined as functorial interpretation
228 of concepts into a background of intuition or models; Eilenberg and Moore, 1965; Lawvere,
229 1994, 2004a). As such, functorial semantics is the objective logic (as defined in Lawvere, 1994,
230 p. 43) of consciousness.

231

232

233

234 **Conclusions**

235 We defined conscious experience as an object of the category of conscious experiences, which
236 aligns with the intuitions engendered by our everyday experiences with objects (cf. a table is an
237 object of a category of tables). It is fascinating to note that the most advanced scientific
238 understanding of object (as an object of a category of objects; Lawvere, 2015) is in accord with
239 our ordinary experience. The category of conscious experiences provides the conceptual
240 repertoire—basic shapes, figures, and incidences—needed to develop an adequately explicit
241 theory of conscious experience. Given that the objective logic intrinsic to conscious experiences
242 is not classical for a variety of abstract essences of consciousness that we considered, it would be
243 interesting to compare the objective logic of consciousness with quantum logic that was found to
244 better account for cognition compared to the classical logic (Roy, 2016).

245

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252

Appendices**253 A1. Category of Idempotents**

254 Let's consider, within the framework of Hopfield model (1982), a neural network consisting of
255 two neurons coding for two features. For a given stimulus, a neuron can respond with a decrease,
256 constant, or increase in its firing rate. So, we have nine 1×2 vectors as possible sensations S:

257 $S_1 = [-1 \ -1]$

258 $S_2 = [-1 \ 0]$

259 $S_3 = [-1 \ +1]$

260 $S_4 = [0 \ -1]$

261 $S_5 = [0 \ 0]$

262 $S_6 = [0 \ +1]$

263 $S_7 = [+1 \ -1]$

264 $S_8 = [+1 \ 0]$

265 $S_9 = [+1 \ +1]$

266 We define memory as a synaptic weight matrix M with entries given by associative learning:

267
$$m_{ij} = s_i \times s_j$$

268 where (subscripts) i, j index the two neurons. For example, memory M_1 of sensation S_1 is:

$$269 \quad M_1 = S_1^T \times S_1$$

270 (T denotes transpose), which is a 2×2 weight matrix. Substituting the values of sensation S_1 , we
271 find:

$$272 \quad M_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

273 Next, we define perception P as an action of memory M on sensation S :

$$274 \quad P = S \times M$$

275 With memory $M = M_1$, we find the percepts resulting from the action of memory M_1 on the nine
276 sensations:

$$277 \quad P_1 = S_1 \times M_1 = 2[-1 \ -1]$$

$$278 \quad P_2 = S_2 \times M_1 = [-1 \ -1]$$

$$279 \quad P_3 = S_3 \times M_1 = [0 \ 0]$$

$$280 \quad P_4 = S_4 \times M_1 = [-1 \ -1]$$

$$281 \quad P_5 = S_5 \times M_1 = [0 \ 0]$$

$$282 \quad P_6 = S_6 \times M_1 = [+1 \ +1]$$

$$283 \quad P_7 = S_7 \times M_1 = [0 \ 0]$$

284 $P_8 = S_8 \times M_1 = [+1 +1]$

285 $P_9 = S_9 \times M_1 = 2[+1 +1]$

286 Note that P_1 , P_5 , and P_9 are fixed-points (with, say, S_1 as initial state and $P_1 (= S_1)$ as final state in
 287 the language of dynamical systems), while sensations S_1 , S_2 , and S_4 perceived as P_1 ; sensations
 288 S_3 , S_5 , and S_7 perceived as P_5 ; sensations S_6 , S_8 , and S_9 perceived as P_9 . The dynamics of action
 289 of memory on sensation has the structure of idempotents as displayed below:

290

291

292

293

294 The above neural network can be formalized with action P of memory M on sensation S defined
 295 as a map:

296

$$P: S \times M \rightarrow S$$

297 For a neural network of N neurons, memories M are $N \times N$ matrices, which when thought of
 298 endomaps $N \rightarrow N$, and with matrix multiplication as composition (of endomaps; MacLane, 1998,
 299 p. 11), form a monoid (Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 167). The $N \times N$ matrix with all
 300 diagonal elements as 1 serves as monoid identity (ibid, p. 77), while the $N \times N$ matrix with all

301 entries as 0 is a constant C , since $C \times M = C$ for all memories M . Since this is the only constant
 302 of the monoid of memories, the category of actions (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p. 360):

$$303 \quad P: S \times M \rightarrow S$$

304 forms a topos of idempotents (ibid, p. 367), i.e. a category with truth value object. The truth
 305 value object of the category of idempotents has three truth values:

$$306 \quad V = \{false, u, true\}$$

307 equipped with an idempotent endomap:

$$308 \quad v: V \rightarrow V$$

309 defined as

310 $v(false) = false$, $v(u) = true$, and $v(true) = true$.

311 Categorical perception, wherein a particular (rose) is perceived as an exemplar of a general
 312 (flower), also has the structure of idempotents (see also Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p. 106):

316 Given the splitting of idempotent endomaps into section-retract pairs, the category of
 317 idempotents can also be characterized in terms of the opposite pair of section-retract maps,

318 wherein the basic shapes are particulars and generals, while sorting and exemplifying are the
 319 incidence relations between the two basic shapes (Kathpalia, Posina, and Nagaraj, 2017).

320 We now calculate the truth value object of the category of idempotents. Truth value object of
 321 the category of idempotents is an object of the category of idempotents (just as in the case of
 322 sets, where a two-element set $\mathbf{2} = \{\text{false}, \text{true}\}$ is the truth value object of the category of sets).
 323 An object of the category of idempotents (modelled in the category of sets) is a set A equipped
 324 with an idempotent endomap

$$325 \quad a: A \rightarrow A$$

326 satisfying

$$327 \quad a \circ a = a.$$

328 where ‘ \circ ’ denotes composition of maps. A map f from an idempotent a to an idempotent b
 329 (where $b: B \rightarrow B$ satisfying $b \circ b = b$) is a function

$$330 \quad f: A \rightarrow B$$

331 satisfying

$$332 \quad f \circ a = b \circ f.$$

333 The truth value object of a category is defined as an object representing every part
 334 (monomorphism) of any object of the category. The truth value object can be calculated in terms
 335 of the inverse images of parts of basic shapes along incidence relations (structural maps). Basic

336 shapes along with incidence relations constitute the abstract essence or the theory of a given
 337 category. What are the basic shapes and their incidences constituting the theory of category of
 338 idempotents? The theory of idempotents consists of a generic idempotent E , along with an [non-
 339 identity] idempotent endomap e on E (as shown below):

344 The basic shape E along with the incidence relation e together constitute the theory subcategory
 345 \mathcal{E} of the category of idempotents. The basic shape E has three parts *false*, u , and *true* (shown
 346 below), which, by the definition of truth value object, correspond to three E -shaped figures (truth
 347 values) in the truth value object of the category of idempotents.

351 The idempotent endomap $v: V \rightarrow V$, where $V = \{false, u, true\}$, is given by the inverse images of
 352 the three parts along the incidence relation $e: E \rightarrow E$. The inverse image of the part *false* along e
 353 is *false*; the inverse image of the part u along e is *true*; and the inverse image of the part *true*

354 along e is also *true*. Putting it all together we obtain the truth value object v (depicted below) of
 355 the category of idempotents.

358 Based on the truth value object v , logical operations negation, *AND*, and *OR* can be defined.
 359 Given a part P of an object A (of the category of idempotents), the familiar negation $not(P)$ is
 360 defined as the largest part of A whose intersection with P is empty. Dually, another negation
 361 $non(P)$ is defined as the smallest part of A whose union with P is the whole object A . In the
 362 category of sets, both negation operations— not , non —are identical. However, in the category of
 363 idempotents, these two negation operations can give different results (as shown below). The
 364 negation operation non allows logical contradiction: $P \text{ AND } non(P)$, which is boundary in
 365 geometric terminology (Lawvere, 1986, 1991; Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 201).

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 367
 368
 369
 370 Furthermore, double negation can be bigger or smaller than identity depending on the nature of
 371 negation as shown below:

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373

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375

376

377 A2. Illusion-free Perception

378 Consider a set A and a set V of values of properties of A . A function

379

$$p: A \rightarrow V$$

380 is a V -valued property of the set A . The set of all V -valued properties of A (or more broadly, the

381 set of all functions from the domain set A to the codomain set V) is the map set V^A . The set V^A

382 of properties, in turn, has properties, which are functionals

383

$$q: V^A \rightarrow V$$

384 where the functional q is a V -valued property of the set V^A of all V -valued properties of A . Our

385 objective is to reconstruct the set A from the set $V^{(V^A)}$ of properties of its V -valued properties

386 (Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 125-126, 148-152). Towards this end, we define generalized

387 point. First recollect that a point of a set A is a function

388

$$a: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$$

389 where $\mathbf{1} = \{*\}$ is the terminal set of the category of sets, i.e. a single-element set; hence points of
 390 a set correspond to its elements. Since elements of set completely characterize a set, we define
 391 generalized point so as to establish a 1-1 correspondence between points and generalized points
 392 (perceived elements).

393 A V -generalized point of the set A is a functional

$$394 \quad q: V^A \rightarrow V$$

395 such that for each V -valued property of A

$$396 \quad p: A \rightarrow V$$

397 and for every endomap of the property type V

$$398 \quad e: V \rightarrow V$$

399 the following equation is satisfied:

$$400 \quad q(e \circ p) = e(q(p))$$

401 where ' \circ ' denotes composition of functions and parentheses denote evaluation of functions.

402 Let's first consider the left-hand side

$$403 \quad q(e \circ p)$$

404 The V -valued property of A

$$405 \quad p: A \rightarrow V$$

406 is an element of the set V^A of all V -valued properties of A . Furthermore, since the codomain V
 407 of p is same as the domain V of

$$408 \quad e: V \rightarrow V$$

409 we can compose them to obtain a composite

$$410 \quad e \circ p = A \rightarrow V \rightarrow V = A \rightarrow V$$

411 which is also an element of the set V^A of all V -valued properties of A ; and hence when the
 412 functional

$$413 \quad q: V^A \rightarrow V$$

414 is evaluated at ' $e \circ p$ ' gives an element ' v ' of the set V of values

$$415 \quad q(e \circ p) = v$$

416 Let us now consider the right-hand side

$$417 \quad e(q(p))$$

418 Once again

$$419 \quad p: A \rightarrow V$$

420 is a V -valued property of A , i.e. an element of the set V^A of all V -valued properties of A . Hence
 421 evaluating the functional

$$422 \quad q: V^A \rightarrow V$$

423 at p gives a value

424 $q(p)$

425 which is an element of the set V of values. Hence the endomap

426 $e: V \rightarrow V$

427 when evaluated at the element ' $q(p)$ ' of domain set V gives an element of V , i.e.

428 $e(q(p)) = v'$

429 Summing up, the functional

430 $q: V^A \rightarrow V$

431 is a V -generalized point of A (perceived element of A) if for every

432 $p: A \rightarrow V$

433 and for every

434 $e: V \rightarrow V$

435 we find that

436 $q(e \circ p) = e(q(p))$

437 or in terms of our above example

438 $v = v'$.

439 Returning to our main objective, i.e., establishing an isomorphism between points and
 440 perceived elements (generalized points) involves finding a property type V such that for every
 441 set A , the V -generalized points of A , i.e. the functionals

$$442 \quad q: V^A \rightarrow V$$

443 satisfying

$$444 \quad q(e \circ p) = e(q(p))$$

445 for every

$$446 \quad p: A \rightarrow V$$

447 and for every

$$448 \quad e: V \rightarrow V$$

449 are in 1-1 correspondence with the points

$$450 \quad a: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$$

451 of the set A .

452 We give an example of perceived elements (generalized points) corresponding to points of a set.

453 Let $A = \{a_1, a_2\}$ be the object of our investigation and $V = \{0, 1\}$ be the property type. There are
 454 two points in A

$$455 \quad a_1: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$$

456 and

457 $a2: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$

458 Now let's calculate the number of generalized points. First, there are four functions from A to V,

459 i.e., four V-valued properties of A, $p: A \rightarrow V$ ($V^A = 2^2 = 4$)

460 $p1: A \rightarrow V; p1(a1) = 0, p1(a2) = 0$

461 $p2: A \rightarrow V; p2(a1) = 1, p2(a2) = 0$

462 $p3: A \rightarrow V; p3(a1) = 0, p3(a2) = 1$

463 $p4: A \rightarrow V; p4(a1) = 1, p4(a2) = 1$

464 Thus,

465 $V^A = \{p1, p2, p3, p4\}$

466 Next, there are 16 functionals, $q: V^A \rightarrow V$ ($V^{(V^A)} = 2^{(2^2)} = 16$)

467 $q1: V^A \rightarrow V; q1(p1) = 0, q1(p2) = 0, q1(p3) = 0, q1(p4) = 0$

468 $q2: V^A \rightarrow V; q2(p1) = 1, q2(p2) = 0, q2(p3) = 0, q2(p4) = 0$

469 $q3: V^A \rightarrow V; q3(p1) = 0, q3(p2) = 1, q3(p3) = 0, q3(p4) = 0$

470 $q4: V^A \rightarrow V; q4(p1) = 1, q4(p2) = 1, q4(p3) = 0, q4(p4) = 0$

471 $q5: V^A \rightarrow V; q5(p1) = 0, q5(p2) = 0, q5(p3) = 1, q5(p4) = 0$

472 $q6: V^A \rightarrow V; q6(p1) = 1, q6(p2) = 0, q6(p3) = 1, q6(p4) = 0$

473 $q7: V^A \rightarrow V; q7(p1) = 0, q7(p2) = 1, q7(p3) = 1, q7(p4) = 0$

474 $q_8: V^A \rightarrow V; q_8(p_1) = 1, q_8(p_2) = 1, q_8(p_3) = 1, q_8(p_4) = 0$

475 $q_9: V^A \rightarrow V; q_9(p_1) = 0, q_9(p_2) = 0, q_9(p_3) = 0, q_9(p_4) = 1$

476 $q_{10}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{10}(p_1) = 1, q_{10}(p_2) = 0, q_{10}(p_3) = 0, q_{10}(p_4) = 1$

477 $q_{11}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{11}(p_1) = 0, q_{11}(p_2) = 1, q_{11}(p_3) = 0, q_{11}(p_4) = 1$

478 $q_{12}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{12}(p_1) = 1, q_{12}(p_2) = 1, q_{12}(p_3) = 0, q_{12}(p_4) = 1$

479 $q_{13}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{13}(p_1) = 0, q_{13}(p_2) = 0, q_{13}(p_3) = 1, q_{13}(p_4) = 1$

480 $q_{14}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{14}(p_1) = 1, q_{14}(p_2) = 0, q_{14}(p_3) = 1, q_{14}(p_4) = 1$

481 $q_{15}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{15}(p_1) = 0, q_{15}(p_2) = 1, q_{15}(p_3) = 1, q_{15}(p_4) = 1$

482 $q_{16}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{16}(p_1) = 1, q_{16}(p_2) = 1, q_{16}(p_3) = 1, q_{16}(p_4) = 1$

483 Of these 16 functionals, there are only two V -generalized points of A corresponding to the two
 484 points of $A = \{a_1, a_2\}$. The two V -generalized points of A are

485 $q_{11}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{11}(p_1) = 0, q_{11}(p_2) = 1, q_{11}(p_3) = 0, q_{11}(p_4) = 1$

486 and

487 $q_{13}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{13}(p_1) = 0, q_{13}(p_2) = 0, q_{13}(p_3) = 1, q_{13}(p_4) = 1$

488 i.e. they both satisfy

489
$$q(e \circ p) = e(q(p))$$

490 Let's consider the functional

491 $q11: V^A \rightarrow V; q11(p1) = 0, q11(p2) = 1, q11(p3) = 0, q11(p4) = 1$

492 In order for the functional $q11$ to be a V -generalized point of A , it has to satisfy

493
$$q11(e \circ p) = e(q11(p))$$

494 for all four $p: A \rightarrow V$ and all four endomaps $e: V \rightarrow V$. They are

495
$$e1: V \rightarrow V; e1(0) = 0, e1(1) = 0$$

496
$$e2: V \rightarrow V; e2(0) = 1, e2(1) = 0$$

497
$$e3: V \rightarrow V; e3(0) = 0, e3(1) = 1$$

498
$$e4: V \rightarrow V; e4(0) = 1, e4(1) = 1$$

499 So, the set of all endomaps of property type V is $V^V = \{e1, e2, e3, e4\}$.

500 Thus, there are 16 cases we have to evaluate to show that the functional

501 $q11: V^A \rightarrow V; q11(p1) = 0, q11(p2) = 1, q11(p3) = 0, q11(p4) = 1$

502 is a V -generalized point of A .

503 Case 1: $(p1, e1)$

504
$$q11(e1 \circ p1) = e1(q11(p1))$$

505 LHS: $q11(e1 \circ p1) = q11(p1) = 0$

506 RHS: $e1(q11(p1)) = e1(0) = 0$

507 Case 2: $(p2, e1)$

$$508 \quad q11(e1 \circ p2) = e1(q11(p2))$$

$$509 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e1 \circ p2) = q11(p1) = 0$$

$$510 \quad \text{RHS: } e1(q11(p2)) = e1(1) = 0$$

511 Case 3: $(p3, e1)$

$$512 \quad q11(e1 \circ p3) = e1(q11(p3))$$

$$513 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e1 \circ p3) = q11(p1) = 0$$

$$514 \quad \text{RHS: } e1(q11(p3)) = e1(0) = 0$$

515 Case 4: $(p4, e1)$

$$516 \quad q11(e1 \circ p4) = e1(q11(p4))$$

$$517 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e1 \circ p4) = q11(p1) = 0$$

$$518 \quad \text{RHS: } e1(q11(p4)) = e1(1) = 0$$

$$519 \quad q11: \mathbb{V}^A \rightarrow \mathbb{V}; q11(p1) = 0, q11(p2) = 1, q11(p3) = 0, q11(p4) = 1$$

520 Case 5: $(p1, e2)$

$$521 \quad q11(e2 \circ p1) = e2(q11(p1))$$

$$522 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e2 \circ p1) = q11(p4) = 1$$

$$523 \quad \text{RHS: } e2(q11(p1)) = e2(0) = 1$$

524 Case 6: $(p2, e2)$

$$525 \quad q11 (e2 \circ p2) = e2 (q11 (p2))$$

$$526 \quad \text{LHS: } q11 (e2 \circ p2) = q11 (p3) = 0$$

$$527 \quad \text{RHS: } e2 (q11 (p2)) = e2 (1) = 0$$

528 Case 7: $(p3, e2)$

$$529 \quad q11 (e2 \circ p3) = e2 (q11 (p3))$$

$$530 \quad \text{LHS: } q11 (e2 \circ p3) = q11 (p2) = 1$$

$$531 \quad \text{RHS: } e2 (q11 (p3)) = e2 (0) = 1$$

532 Case 8: $(p4, e2)$

$$533 \quad q11 (e2 \circ p4) = e2 (q11 (p4))$$

$$534 \quad \text{LHS: } q11 (e2 \circ p4) = q11 (p1) = 0$$

$$535 \quad \text{RHS: } e2 (q11 (p4)) = e2 (1) = 0$$

$$536 \quad q11: \mathbb{V}^A \rightarrow \mathbb{V}; q11(p1) = 0, q11(p2) = 1, q11(p3) = 0, q11(p4) = 1$$

537 Case 9: $(p1, e3)$

$$538 \quad q11 (e3 \circ p1) = e3 (q11 (p1))$$

$$539 \quad \text{LHS: } q11 (e3 \circ p1) = q11 (p1) = 0$$

$$540 \quad \text{RHS: } e3 (q11 (p1)) = e3 (0) = 0$$

541 Case 10: $(p2, e3)$

$$542 \quad q11(e3 \circ p2) = e3(q11(p2))$$

$$543 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e3 \circ p2) = q11(p2) = 1$$

$$544 \quad \text{RHS: } e3(q11(p2)) = e3(1) = 1$$

545 Case 11: $(p3, e3)$

$$546 \quad q11(e3 \circ p3) = e3(q11(p3))$$

$$547 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e3 \circ p3) = q11(p3) = 0$$

$$548 \quad \text{RHS: } e3(q11(p3)) = e3(0) = 0$$

549 Case 12: $(p4, e3)$

$$550 \quad q11(e3 \circ p4) = e3(q11(p4))$$

$$551 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e3 \circ p4) = q11(p4) = 1$$

$$552 \quad \text{RHS: } e3(q11(p4)) = e3(1) = 1$$

$$553 \quad q11: \mathbb{V}^A \rightarrow \mathbb{V}; q11(p1) = 0, q11(p2) = 1, q11(p3) = 0, q11(p4) = 1$$

554 Case 13: $(p1, e4)$

$$555 \quad q11(e4 \circ p1) = e4(q11(p1))$$

$$556 \quad \text{LHS: } q11(e4 \circ p1) = q11(p1) = 0$$

$$557 \quad \text{RHS: } e4(q11(p1)) = e4(0) = 0$$

558 Case 14: $(p2, e4)$

559
$$q11 (e4 \circ p2) = e4 (q11 (p2))$$

560 LHS: $q11 (e4 \circ p2) = q11 (p4) = 1$

561 RHS: $e4 (q11 (p2)) = e4 (1) = 1$

562 Case 15: $(p3, e4)$

563
$$q11 (e4 \circ p3) = e4 (q11 (p3))$$

564 LHS: $q11 (e4 \circ p3) = q11 (p4) = 1$

565 RHS: $e4 (q11 (p3)) = e4 (0) = 1$

566 Case 16: $(p4, e4)$

567
$$q11 (e4 \circ p4) = e4 (q11 (p4))$$

568 LHS: $q11 (e4 \circ p4) = q11 (p4) = 1$

569 RHS: $e4 (q11 (p4)) = e4 (1) = 1$

570 Thus, the functional

571
$$q11: V^A \rightarrow V; q11(p1) = 0, q11(p2) = 1, q11(p3) = 0, q11(p4) = 1$$

572 is a V-generalized point of A. Along similar lines, we can show that the functional

573
$$q13: V^A \rightarrow V; q13(p1) = 0, q13(p2) = 0, q13(p3) = 1, q13(p4) = 1$$

574 is another V-generalized point of A. These two perceived elements (generalized points)

575 correspond to the two points

576 $a1: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$

577 $a2: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$

578 of the set $A = \{a1, a2\}$.

579 Next, we give an example of a functional (one of the remaining 14 functionals of the total 16
580 functionals) which is not a generalized point. Consider the functional

581 $q12: V^A \rightarrow V; q12(p1) = 1, q12(p2) = 1, q12(p3) = 0, q12(p4) = 1$

582 In order to be a V -generalized point of A , the functional

583 $q12: V^A \rightarrow V$

584 must satisfy

585 $q12(e \circ p) = e(q12(p))$

586 for all p in $V^A = \{p1, p2, p3, p4\}$ and for all e in $V^V = \{e1, e2, e3, e4\}$, i.e., for all 16 cases we

587 evaluated earlier. Let's consider the case of $p = p1$ and $e = e1$. We have to check for the equality

588 $q12(e1 \circ p1) = e1(q12(p1))$

589 LHS: $q12(e1 \circ p1) = q12(p1) = 1$

590 RHS: $e1(q12(p1)) = e1(1) = 0$

591 Since LHS is not equal to RHS, the functional

592 $q12: V^A \rightarrow V; q12(p1) = 1, q12(p2) = 1, q12(p3) = 0, q12(p4) = 1$

593 is not a V -generalized point of A .

594 Now we spell out how each point of a set gives rise to a generalized point (perceived element).

595 Consider a set A and a type V . Since generalized point is a functional

$$596 \quad q: V^A \rightarrow V$$

597 we first construct a functional called evaluation functional for each element 'a' of the set A .

598 Recollect that the elements of domain set V^A of the functional q are V -valued properties of A ,

599 i.e.

$$600 \quad p: A \rightarrow V$$

601 and the functional q assigns to each p in V^A an element 'v' of the codomain set V of the

602 functional q . An evaluation functional corresponding to an element 'a' of the set A is defined as

$$603 \quad q_a: V^A \rightarrow V$$

604 with

$$605 \quad q_a(p) = p(a)$$

606 Now we show that this evaluation functional is a generalized point, i.e. satisfies

$$607 \quad q_a(e \circ p) = e(q_a(p))$$

608 where

$$609 \quad e: V \rightarrow V$$

610 is an endomap on the type V of property.

611 LHS: $q_a(e \circ p) = (e \circ p)(a) = e(p(a))$

612 RHS: $e(q_a(p)) = e(p(a))$

613 Thus, the evaluation functional corresponding to each point of a set is a generalized point

614 (Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 150). We now give an example of this general result.

615 Consider a set $A = \{a1, a2, a3\}$ and a property type $V = \{0, 1\}$. The set V^A of all V -valued

616 properties of A consists of 8 functions, i.e.

$$617 \quad V^A = \{p1, p2, p3, p4, p5, p6, p7, p8\}$$

618 where

$$619 \quad p1: A \rightarrow V; p1(a1) = 0, p1(a2) = 0, p1(a3) = 0$$

$$620 \quad p2: A \rightarrow V; p2(a1) = 1, p2(a2) = 0, p2(a3) = 0$$

$$621 \quad p3: A \rightarrow V; p3(a1) = 0, p3(a2) = 1, p3(a3) = 0$$

$$622 \quad p4: A \rightarrow V; p4(a1) = 1, p4(a2) = 1, p4(a3) = 0$$

$$623 \quad p5: A \rightarrow V; p5(a1) = 0, p5(a2) = 0, p5(a3) = 1$$

$$624 \quad p6: A \rightarrow V; p6(a1) = 1, p6(a2) = 0, p6(a3) = 1$$

$$625 \quad p7: A \rightarrow V; p7(a1) = 0, p7(a2) = 1, p7(a3) = 1$$

$$626 \quad p8: A \rightarrow V; p8(a1) = 1, p8(a2) = 1, p8(a3) = 1$$

627 Let us now consider a point

628 $a1: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$

629 and the corresponding evaluation functional

630 $q_{a1}: V^A \rightarrow V$

631 defined as

632 $q_{a1}(p) = p(a1)$

633 for all p in V^A , i.e.

634 $q_{a1}(p1) = p1(a1) = 0$

635 $q_{a1}(p2) = p2(a1) = 1$

636 $q_{a1}(p3) = p3(a1) = 0$

637 $q_{a1}(p4) = p4(a1) = 1$

638 $q_{a1}(p5) = p5(a1) = 0$

639 $q_{a1}(p6) = p6(a1) = 1$

640 $q_{a1}(p7) = p7(a1) = 0$

641 $q_{a1}(p8) = p8(a1) = 1$

642 Now we have to show that this evaluation functional

643 $q_{a1}: V^A \rightarrow V$

644 satisfies

$$645 \quad q_{al}(e \circ p) = e(q_{al}(p))$$

646 for all elements (V-valued properties of A) p in $V^A = \{p1, p2, p3, p4, p5, p6, p7, p8\}$, and for all

647 elements (endomaps of property type V) e in $V^V = \{e1, e2, e3, e4\}$ defined as

$$648 \quad e1: V \rightarrow V; e1(0) = 0, e1(1) = 0$$

$$649 \quad e2: V \rightarrow V; e2(0) = 1, e2(1) = 0$$

$$650 \quad e3: V \rightarrow V; e3(0) = 0, e3(1) = 1$$

$$651 \quad e4: V \rightarrow V; e4(0) = 1, e4(1) = 1$$

652 Thus we have to test for the equality

$$653 \quad q_{al}(e \circ p) = e(q_{al}(p))$$

654 in 32 cases. They are:

655 Case 1: $(p1, e1)$

$$656 \quad q_{al}(e1 \circ p1) = e1(q_{al}(p1))$$

$$657 \quad \text{LHS: } q_{al}(e1 \circ p1) = q_{al}(p1) = 0$$

$$658 \quad \text{RHS: } e1(q_{al}(p1)) = e1(0) = 0$$

659 Case 2: $(p2, e1)$

$$660 \quad q_{al}(e1 \circ p2) = e1(q_{al}(p2))$$

661 LHS: $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p2) = q_{a1}(p1) = 0$

662 RHS: $e1(q_{a1}(p2)) = e1(1) = 0$

663 Case 3: $(p3, e1)$

664 $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p3) = e1(q_{a1}(p3))$

665 LHS: $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p3) = q_{a1}(p1) = 0$

666 RHS: $e1(q_{a1}(p3)) = e1(0) = 0$

667 Case 4: $(p4, e1)$

668 $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p4) = e1(q_{a1}(p4))$

669 LHS: $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p4) = q_{a1}(p1) = 0$

670 RHS: $e1(q_{a1}(p4)) = e1(1) = 0$

671 Case 5: $(p5, e1)$

672 $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p5) = e1(q_{a1}(p5))$

673 LHS: $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p5) = q_{a1}(p1) = 0$

674 RHS: $e1(q_{a1}(p5)) = e1(0) = 0$

675 Case 6: $(p6, e1)$

676 $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p6) = e1(q_{a1}(p6))$

677 LHS: $q_{a1}(e1 \circ p6) = q_{a1}(p1) = 0$

678 RHS: $e1 (q_{a1} (p6)) = e1 (1) = 0$

679 Case 7: $(p7, e1)$

680 $q_{a1} (e1 \circ p7) = e1 (q_{a1} (p7))$

681 LHS: $q_{a1} (e1 \circ p7) = q_{a1} (p1) = 0$

682 RHS: $e1 (q_{a1} (p7)) = e1 (0) = 0$

683 Case 8: $(p8, e1)$

684 $q_{a1} (e1 \circ p8) = e1 (q_{a1} (p8))$

685 LHS: $q_{a1} (e1 \circ p8) = q_{a1} (p1) = 0$

686 RHS: $e1 (q_{a1} (p8)) = e1 (1) = 0$

687 Case 9: $(p1, e2)$

688 $q_{a1} (e2 \circ p1) = e2 (q_{a1} (p1))$

689 LHS: $q_{a1} (e2 \circ p1) = q_{a1} (p8) = 1$

690 RHS: $e2 (q_{a1} (p1)) = e2 (0) = 1$

691 Case 10: $(p2, e2)$

692 $q_{a1} (e2 \circ p2) = e2 (q_{a1} (p2))$

693 LHS: $q_{a1} (e2 \circ p2) = q_{a1} (p7) = 0$

694 RHS: $e2 (q_{a1} (p2)) = e2 (1) = 0$

695 Case 11: $(p3, e2)$

696
$$q_{a1}(e2 \circ p3) = e2(q_{a1}(p3))$$

697 LHS: $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p3) = q_{a1}(p6) = 1$

698 RHS: $e2(q_{a1}(p3)) = e2(0) = 1$

699 Case 12: $(p4, e2)$

700
$$q_{a1}(e2 \circ p4) = e2(q_{a1}(p4))$$

701 LHS: $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p4) = q_{a1}(p5) = 0$

702 RHS: $e2(q_{a1}(p4)) = e2(1) = 0$

703 Case 13: $(p5, e2)$

704
$$q_{a1}(e2 \circ p5) = e2(q_{a1}(p5))$$

705 LHS: $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p5) = q_{a1}(p4) = 1$

706 RHS: $e2(q_{a1}(p5)) = e2(0) = 1$

707 Case 14: $(p6, e2)$

708
$$q_{a1}(e2 \circ p6) = e2(q_{a1}(p6))$$

709 LHS: $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p6) = q_{a1}(p3) = 0$

710 RHS: $e2(q_{a1}(p6)) = e2(1) = 0$

711 Case 15: $(p7, e2)$

712 $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p7) = e2(q_{a1}(p7))$

713 LHS: $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p7) = q_{a1}(p2) = 1$

714 RHS: $e2(q_{a1}(p7)) = e2(0) = 1$

715 Case 16: $(p8, e2)$

716 $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p8) = e2(q_{a1}(p8))$

717 LHS: $q_{a1}(e2 \circ p8) = q_{a1}(p1) = 0$

718 RHS: $e2(q_{a1}(p8)) = e2(1) = 0$

719 Case 17: $(p1, e3)$

720 $q_{a1}(e3 \circ p1) = e3(q_{a1}(p1))$

721 LHS: $q_{a1}(e3 \circ p1) = q_{a1}(p1) = 0$

722 RHS: $e3(q_{a1}(p1)) = e3(0) = 0$

723 Case 18: $(p2, e3)$

724 $q_{a1}(e3 \circ p2) = e3(q_{a1}(p2))$

725 LHS: $q_{a1}(e3 \circ p2) = q_{a1}(p2) = 1$

726 RHS: $e3(q_{a1}(p2)) = e3(1) = 1$

727 Case 19: $(p3, e3)$

728 $q_{a1}(e3 \circ p3) = e3(q_{a1}(p3))$

729 LHS: $q_{al}(e3 \circ p3) = q_{al}(p3) = 0$

730 RHS: $e3(q_{al}(p3)) = e3(0) = 0$

731 Case 20: $(p4, e3)$

732 $q_{al}(e3 \circ p4) = e3(q_{al}(p4))$

733 LHS: $q_{al}(e3 \circ p4) = q_{al}(p4) = 1$

734 RHS: $e3(q_{al}(p4)) = e3(1) = 1$

735 Case 21: $(p5, e3)$

736 $q_{al}(e3 \circ p5) = e3(q_{al}(p5))$

737 LHS: $q_{al}(e3 \circ p5) = q_{al}(p5) = 0$

738 RHS: $e3(q_{al}(p5)) = e3(0) = 0$

739 Case 22: $(p6, e3)$

740 $q_{al}(e3 \circ p6) = e3(q_{al}(p6))$

741 LHS: $q_{al}(e3 \circ p6) = q_{al}(p6) = 1$

742 RHS: $e3(q_{al}(p6)) = e3(1) = 1$

743 Case 23: $(p7, e3)$

744 $q_{al}(e3 \circ p7) = e3(q_{al}(p7))$

745 LHS: $q_{al}(e3 \circ p7) = q_{al}(p7) = 0$

746 RHS: $e3 (q_{a1} (p7)) = e3 (0) = 0$

747 Case 24: $(p8, e3)$

748 $q_{a1} (e3 \circ p8) = e3 (q_{a1} (p8))$

749 LHS: $q_{a1} (e3 \circ p8) = q_{a1} (p8) = 1$

750 RHS: $e3 (q_{a1} (p8)) = e3 (1) = 1$

751 Case 25: $(p1, e4)$

752 $q_{a1} (e4 \circ p1) = e4 (q_{a1} (p1))$

753 LHS: $q_{a1} (e4 \circ p1) = q_{a1} (p8) = 1$

754 RHS: $e4 (q_{a1} (p1)) = e4 (0) = 1$

755 Case 26: $(p2, e4)$

756 $q_{a1} (e4 \circ p2) = e4 (q_{a1} (p2))$

757 LHS: $q_{a1} (e4 \circ p2) = q_{a1} (p8) = 1$

758 RHS: $e4 (q_{a1} (p2)) = e4 (1) = 1$

759 Case 27: $(p3, e4)$

760 $q_{a1} (e4 \circ p3) = e4 (q_{a1} (p3))$

761 LHS: $q_{a1} (e4 \circ p3) = q_{a1} (p8) = 1$

762 RHS: $e4 (q_{a1} (p3)) = e4 (0) = 1$

763 Case 28: $(p4, e4)$

$$764 \quad q_{a1}(e4 \circ p4) = e4(q_{a1}(p4))$$

$$765 \quad \text{LHS: } q_{a1}(e4 \circ p4) = q_{a1}(p8) = 1$$

$$766 \quad \text{RHS: } e4(q_{a1}(p4)) = e4(1) = 1$$

767 Case 29: $(p5, e4)$

$$768 \quad q_{a1}(e4 \circ p5) = e4(q_{a1}(p5))$$

$$769 \quad \text{LHS: } q_{a1}(e4 \circ p5) = q_{a1}(p8) = 1$$

$$770 \quad \text{RHS: } e4(q_{a1}(p5)) = e4(0) = 1$$

771 Case 30: $(p6, e4)$

$$772 \quad q_{a1}(e4 \circ p6) = e4(q_{a1}(p6))$$

$$773 \quad \text{LHS: } q_{a1}(e4 \circ p6) = q_{a1}(p8) = 1$$

$$774 \quad \text{RHS: } e4(q_{a1}(p6)) = e4(1) = 1$$

775 Case 31: $(p7, e4)$

$$776 \quad q_{a1}(e4 \circ p7) = e4(q_{a1}(p7))$$

$$777 \quad \text{LHS: } q_{a1}(e4 \circ p7) = q_{a1}(p8) = 1$$

$$778 \quad \text{RHS: } e4(q_{a1}(p7)) = e4(0) = 1$$

779 Case 32: $(p8, e4)$

780
$$q_{a1}(e4 \circ p8) = e4(q_{a1}(p8))$$

781 LHS: $q_{a1}(e4 \circ p8) = q_{a1}(p8) = 1$

782 RHS: $e4(q_{a1}(p8)) = e4(1) = 1$

783 Thus the evaluation functional

784 $q_{a1}: V^A \rightarrow V; q_{a1}(p1)=0, q_{a1}(p2)=1, q_{a1}(p3)=0, q_{a1}(p4)=1, q_{a1}(p5)=0, q_{a1}(p6)=1, q_{a1}(p7)=0, q_{a1}(p8)=1$

785 satisfying

786
$$q_{a1}(e \circ p) = e(q_{a1}(p))$$

787 (for all $p: A \rightarrow V$ and for all $e: V \rightarrow V$) is a V-generalized point of A corresponding to the point

788
$$a1: \mathbf{1} \rightarrow A$$

789 Along the same lines, we can show that each of remaining two points of the set $A = \{a1, a2, a3\}$

790 give rise to corresponding V-generalized points of A.

791 With property type $V = \mathbf{2}$ (two-element set), although there is a V-generalized point of A

792 corresponding to each point of A, there can also be generalized points that do not correspond to

793 any points of A, which we may call illusions (or ghost points). In order to obtain a 1-1

794 correspondence between points of any set A and V-generalized points of A, i.e. isomorphism

795 between objects and perceived objects, we need a 3-element set as the property type V. One of

796 our objectives is to calculate objects analogous to the 3-element set (in the category of sets) in

797 categories that are reflective of reality such as the category of categories. We plan to approach

798 this goal by calculating the basic types of knowing (objects analogous to 3-element set in the

799 category of sets) in more structured categories such as dynamical systems, functions, graphs, and
800 actions.

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